

WORK LIFE BALANCE OF INDIAN FEMALE DOCTORS DURING THEIR MENSTRUAL CYCLE - A REVIEW IN THE INDIAN CONTEXTS

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Research Guide

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Paper Received On: 20 SEPTEMBER 2025

Peer Reviewed On: 24 OCTOBER 2025

Published On: 01 NOVEMBER 2025

Abstract

The job of female doctors is full of various issues related to night shifts, fewer breaks and higher work tension. As the medical and health care sector is becoming more and more demanding in India, it is important to pay attention to the work life balance of female doctors who are working in hospitals. There are many critical Constraints encountered by female doctors in maintaining their work -life balance, especially in the menstrual cycle period. The Indian female doctors have reported stress and depression during their menstrual cycle; because they are playing multiple roles towards their family members, as well as towards their profession. Through the present literature an attempt has been made to explore the work life balance of the Indian female doctors during their menstrual cycle, and the impact of menstrual cycle on their work capacity or productivity. Apart from this, an attempt has been made to explore the need for menstrual leave policy. This literature focused on the impact of menstrual cycle on the physical and mental health status of female doctors.

Key words - Female doctors, work life balance, menstrual cycle, productivity, work capacity.

Introduction –

Several empirical studies have pointed out that, encountering several constraint and challenges in their routine work during the menstrual cycle. It is often caused for increasing imbalance between their professional and personal life. Intervention of professional life in personal or family life of female doctors has significantly impacted on the perception regarding their profession; and their attitude towards their profession. The intervention of professional life in personal life of female doctors, also negatively impacting on job satisfaction,

commitment etc. working in hospitals is treatment. The work life balance of female doctors who are affected due to heavy work pressure, pressure of scheduled work night shift and mainly affected during their menstrual cycle. Absence of proper work life balance among female doctors is concerned with a many negative on their physical and mental health conditions, and also on the work culture of hospitals, where they are working.

The Indian female doctors like all other general female, encountering many problems-challenges during the menstrual cycle, which includes too much bleeding, irregularity in menstrual cycle and pre-menstrual Syndrome or menstrual dysphoric disorder, menstruation may Significantly negatively be affected on their productivity and also affected on the ability of maintaining work life balance. The work life imbalance of female doctors during their menstruating period has caused to reduce work Capacity, and their productivity. The present literature focused on the work-life balance of female doctors during their menstruation cycle period and its adverse impact on their productivity, physical and mental health Conditions.

Literature Review-

- 1) Asma S. and M. Alrahilli (2020) have pointed out that menstrual Cycle period do effects on the female doctors' working capacity and productivity. Authors have also observed that menstrual cycle period also diversely impacted on the work-life balance of female doctors working in hospitals.
- 2) Fengying and Hualan Cheng, (2023), have attempted to explore the relation -ship between shift work and working women's menstrual features like irregularity in periods, dysmenorrhea and early menopause. Authors have pointed out that working in shift is related to the increased mike risk of menstrual dysfunction.
- 3) Nikita Agarwal, (2014) has discussed on the significance of implementation of menstrual leave policy for working women employees of all Sectors, with the objective of fostering an inclusive environment for women employees. Author has discussed on the socio- cultural problems related to menstruation in India.
- 4) Nirmala m. cond Sudipto mondial, (2020), have attempted to identify the menstrual patterns, abnormalities and effects of menstrual abnormalities on the productivity, physical and mental health conditions of female doctors. Apart from this author have also focused on its impact on the work life balance of Indian female doctors.

Importance of the study

There is a lack of literature or studies in the Context of work life balance and menstrual cycle nerved problems encountered by Indian female doctors, majority of the studies are in

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pertaining to the event common working female employees in various sectors' organizations. Therefore, the present literature may be useful to understand the work life balance of female doctors during their menstrual cycle. The present literature may be useful addition to the available literature pertaining to the menstrual cycle and work life balance of the female employees.

Objectives of the study

- 1) To explore the work life balance of female doctors in their menstrual cycle.
- 2) To focus on the impact of menstrual cycle the productivity, physical and mental health conditions of female doctors.
- 3) To explain the need of menstrual leave policy implementation in India.

Method of Study.

The present study or literature is exclusively based on the secondary information pertaining to the selected topic. The study is elaborative in nature.

Work-life balance of Indian female doctors during menstrual Cycle

The Indian female doctors are encountering various constraints and challenges due to heavy work load, and demanding work environment and expectations of hospital management authority as well as expectations of patients and their relatives. It also adversely impacted on their menstrual health conditions. It caused to increase the occupational stress on them. They often experiencing severe problems in performing the duties and responsibilities towards their family members as well as their organization hospital where they are working. Now a days' female doctors are encountering conflicting demands from their profession and life domains. "The job of female doctors entails many issues which includes working in night shifts, longer duration of working, short period of rest etc. During the menstrual cycle female doctors often experienced physical and mental symptoms like - lack of energy, discomfort feeling, moods change and anxiety. These symptoms create many challenges and constraints in performing there, duties. The pressure of professional stress can make menstrual Symptoms very worse for female doctor. It can disturb their personal and family environment. Therefore, the work life balance becomes a complex task for Indian female doctors. They are struggling between their professional career, development and duties-responsibilities towards family members. Apart from this maintaining a better work-life balance is become difficult for Indian female doctors who are busy with the work schedule which might be adversely affected on their productive

ability at work: "Therefore many female doctors are more likely to alter their job responsibilities or make a profession change to take care of their children and family members.

Even today's modern era, menstruation cycle continues to be perceived negatively in Indian society, despite of several socio-cultural developments have taken place. Therefore, it is difficult for the female doctors to talk freely and openly about their menstrual cycle. Through the many empirical studies, it is found that, majority of female doctors need a substantial time and efforts which is quite impossible for female doctors to spare some time for their fat family obligations. So also, it is not possible for Indian female doctors to be a primary care giver of their children. majority of the empirical studies have been pointed out that, the Indian female doctors working in hospitals, find it difficult to maintain proper balance better their work life and personal-family life, because of Competing work pressure in the hospital and demands of family members at home. In the Indian context, female doctors remain responsible for the family and development of their professional career is rarely get top priority.

Impact of menstrual Cycle on the productivity of female doctors.

The menstrual symptoms may affect the productivity of female doctors. The menstrual cycle period negatively influencing on the female employees in India. The Indian female doctors are not exception for that. The menstrual cycle caused to increase absenteeism where female doctors work while experiencing discomfort. Majority of the studies Concluded that, absence of management support menstrual health responsible to increase the issues associated with productivity.

The duty of female doctors is very important. They must perform their duties as a doctor even if they experiencing pain and discomfort while they are working. It significantly reduces their productivity and concentration on their duties to and responsibilities towards patients. Apart from this, during their menstrual cycle, working in shifts Service rotation, longer working hour etc also factors also caused to increase exhaustion and stress. On this back ground female doctors faced challenges and difficulties to get necessary rest from work with a view to function at their best. Difficulties in getting rest or leisure caused to decrease their productivity. Majority of female doctors are heisted to get help support from their Colleagues when they are on a period. Hormonal imbalance and physical symptoms such as - period pain, fatigue and changes in moods can also adversely impacted on their Concentration, level of energy and overall work performance. Apart from this, Considering the menstrual cycle period as a social signed and lack of Understanding in the Society about menstruation can create a challenging work environment for female doctors to perform their duties effectively at work.

Impact of menstrual cycle on the Physical health Condition of female doctors.

The menstrual cycle period may adversely effects on the Physical health of the female doctors. It may reduce their physical activities. The Physical Symptoms such as. severe pain, bloating can create negative impact on their physical health. Due to During the menstrual period majority of female encountered to a stomach pain, back pain, headaches etc. Due to these issues, there is a significant reduction in their energy levels. It also caused to increase body temperature and Cardiovascular strain. There may be changes in appetite and food craving. Migraines, epilepsy and irritable bowel syndrome may also badly affected on the Physical health of female doctors during the menstrual cycle. During the female doctors encountered to sleep disturbances, insomnia hypersomnia, cramps, breast tenderness etc. Irregularity in menstrual cycle, may cause to increase in the gynaecological issues which create health related problems and may badly impacted on the productivity or working ability of female doctors.

Impact of menstrual cycle on many health condition of female doctors.

The menstrual cycle not only impacts on the productivity and Physical health condition of female doctors but also impacts on their mental health Condition. Physical pain, fatigue and emotional distress can affect a female doctor's cognitive activities decision making ability and capacity to cope with professional stress, which potentially impacting on the patient care. During the menstrual cycle, female often experienced the shifts in hormones, which may cause to change of mood, feeling of depression and anxiety. The symptoms of anxiety may cause to increase imbalance among the personal, Social and professional life of female doctors the mental and emotional challenges can also manifest as physical Symptoms such as fatigue and pain, which may lead to reduce productivity. It also caused to increase service absenteeism and social isolation. Some time, female doctors may face the depressive symptoms which creates temporary cognitive and emotional challenges mate which make impossible to female doctors to perform their professional tastes effectively. Some female doctors experience negative feelings which can decrease their Self-esteem and make it difficult for them to engage socially with, contribute colleagues, patients and also with management authorities. It may to feeling of isolation, depressed mood and feeling of hopelessness, and also caused to reduce their interest towards usual activities or professional. functions. The menstrual cycle caused to increase irritability and affects negatively on the minds of female doctors. It also led to create conflicts and decreased social involvement and contributing to feelings of social isolation.

Need of menstrual leave policy implementation in India.

There is a need of menstrual cycle leave policy in India, with a view to Support the health and well-being of menstruating female employees, reduce their absenteeism, promotion of gender equality and increase the inclusivity of female employees at work. The implementation of menstrual leave policy is essential for improving productivity by allowing female employees to take short work break. menstrual leave policy normalizes. The proper implementation of most during their menstrual period. menstruation period for working female, lead to retention and more stable and efficient female workforce. The implementation of menstrual leave policy is required to create more inclusive and conducive work environment in the organization. It helps to boost up the female employees" morale and loyalty. The Article of 15 (3) of Indian Constitution included the special provisions for female employees, making a menstrual leave policy a potentially Constitutional approach to support female employers health and Condition of work. It is observed that menstrual leave policy is neither regulated under any legal acting status in India or any corporate or industrial organizations. The implementation of menstrual leave policy will not only useful for the female excited to perform their duties towards patients in a more efficient manner, but also increase the productivity as positive work environment. It allows them to concentrate on their responsibilities. The legal provisions or policy pertaining to menstrual leave should be of acknowledging the problems and challenges encountering by female employees during the menstruation cycle at work place. A legislative provisions or patty policy varing is essential to reduce the taboo of culture of menstruation as it realized the stigma.

In Conclusion

Menstrual cycle sometimes caused to reduced. female workforce involvement in their assigned work through reduced productivity and increased work absenteeism. Female doctors employed in large hospitals are not exception for this. menstrual cycle affects the majority of female doctors at certain points in their survival. The present literature tends to explore the work life balance of Indian female doctors during the menstrual Cycle; and explore the impact of menstrual cycle on their productivity, physical health and mental health Conditions. The present study has employed a qualitative or descriptive research method to explore the impact of menstrual cycle on the work life balance, physical and mental health Conditions of female doctors. This literature. study also highlighted the need of implementation of legislative policy of ahead menstrual leave, which it may be helpful to improvised health status of female employees in every sectors. Proper implementation of menstrual leave policy will lead to obtain

work efficiency in crucial events, and it will reduce turnover intentions and attrition plans of female doctors. There should be Comprehensive approach including awareness, access and inclusivity to ensure the wellbeing and empowerment of a female doctors in managing their menstrual health at work place.

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